

Apparent relations between the physical constants G , h and k and physical units

Zhe Lu

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Abstract. The state probability of a hypothetical system is evaluated according to the Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics. The system has two energetic states without free energy, i.e., its partition function $Z = 1$. The energy level of one state is set to be equal to the geometric mean of gravitational energy and photon energy. Either type of energy is defined by the corresponding physical constant and relevant physical quantities, each of which is assigned a unity value. In the

units kg , km , s and K , the probability of the state is given by $e^{-\frac{\sqrt{G\frac{kg^2}{km}h\frac{1}{s}}}{kK}} = \frac{1.00}{\varphi}$, rearranged to

$\frac{kg}{\sqrt{km \cdot sK}} = \frac{k \ln 1.00 \varphi}{\sqrt{Gh}}$, where the geometric-ratio-constant $\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ and the number 1.00 indicates

the condition of three significant digits. Thus, the defined portion of the probability space is

approximated by $\frac{1}{\varphi}$, and $\frac{kg}{\sqrt{km \cdot sK}}$ approximately equals the compound constant $\frac{k \ln \varphi}{\sqrt{Gh}}$. On the Planck

scale, the corresponding relations are expected to be $e^{-\frac{\sqrt{G\frac{m_p^2}{l_p}h\frac{1}{t_p}}}{kT_p}} = \frac{1}{e}$ and $\frac{m_p}{\sqrt{l_p t_p T_p}} = \frac{k}{\sqrt{Gh}}$.

Introduction

The Newtonian constant of gravitation (G), the Planck constant (h) and the Boltzmann constant (k) are three basic physical constants. According to Newton's law, the amount of the gravitational force between two objects with the mass M_1 and M_2 is expressed as

$$F_G = G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r^2} \quad (1)$$

where r is the distance between the two objects. Derived from this relation, the gravitational (potential) energy between two objects is given by

$$U_G = -G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r}. \quad (2)$$

In the Planck relation, the electromagnetic energy carried by a photon is expressed as

$$E_h = h\nu. \quad (3)$$

The Boltzmann entropy (S) was expressed by Planck as

$$S = k \ln W \quad (4)$$

related to energy by the absolute temperature T in the unit K as

$$E_k = kT \ln W \quad (5)$$

where W is the so-called thermodynamic probability.

The values of k and h have been accurately determined to the seventh and the ninth significant digits, respectively. The Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA) fixed the value of k to $1.380649 \times 10^{-23} (kg\ m^2\ s^{-2}\ K^{-1})$ and that of h to $6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} (kg\ m^2\ s^{-1})$, both with zero uncertainty [1-3]. In contrast, the weakness of gravitational interactions and the inability to shield gravitational effects make it extremely challenging to determine G [4,5]. In 2018, CODATA used a pool of 16 sets of experimental measurements of G , which were determined in the last three decades, as the basis of their most recently recommended G of $6.67430 \times 10^{-11} kg^{-1}\ m^3\ s^{-2}$ [1,6]. However, these underlying experimental estimates agree only on the first three significant digits 6.67 [1].

It is perhaps noteworthy that as the outcome of a piece of self-assigned homework, an apparent relation between G and h was derived on the basis of the quantitative equivalence between a gold-ratio- φ -based partition of a probability space and the arithmetic average of comparable amounts of gravitational energy and photon energy [7]. The relative portions of these two types of energy are fixed at the near-unity ratio of the significant digits of G and h . This relation predicts all six digits of the CODATA-recommended G from those of h .

In this summary of a second piece of self-assigned homework, an evaluation of the relations between the energy levels (E_1 and E_2) and the probabilities (p_1 and p_2) of two states in a hypothetic system is described. The entire evaluation was performed on the basis of three significant digits. As it stands, the resulting approximate-equality-expressions are not extendable beyond three digits, except for those true equality-expressions in the Planck units. It must be emphasized whether part of the outcome of this evaluation, or even its entirety, has already been known is not adequately checked.

Evaluation of a hypothetical system

The level of energy in each of the two states in the system without free energy, i.e., the partition function $Z = 1$, is specified on the basis of the geometric mean of gravitational energy and photon energy. Either type of energy is calculated from the corresponding physical constant and relevant physical quantities, each of which is assigned a unity value. For ease of comparison, the units kg , km (instead of m), s and K are used in the initial evaluation such that

$$G = 6.67 \times 10^{-20} kg^{-1} km^3 s^{-2}; \quad (6)$$

$$h = 6.63 \times 10^{-40} kg km^2 s^{-1}; \quad (7)$$

$$k = 1.38 \times 10^{-29} kg km^2 s^{-2} K^{-1}. \quad (8)$$

The outcome of this evaluation will also be given afterwards in the SI units kg , m , s and K .

The geometric mean of gravitational energy and photon energy is given by

$$\sqrt{-U_G E_h} = \sqrt{G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r} h \nu} \quad (9)$$

which is used to define the energy level of state 1 as

$$E_1 = \sqrt{G \frac{M_1 M_2}{r} h \nu} = \sqrt{G \frac{kg^2}{km} h \frac{1}{s}} \quad (10)$$

where for simplicity, the assigned unity value in front of each physical unit is omitted. According to the Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics, the probability of state i may be expressed as

$$p_i = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-\beta E_i} \quad (11)$$

where

$$Z = \sum_{i=1}^N e^{-\beta E_i}. \quad (12)$$

Given here $Z = 1$,

$$p_1 = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-\frac{\sqrt{G \frac{kg^2}{km} h \frac{1}{s}}}{kK}} = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-\frac{\sqrt{6.67 \times 6.63 \times 10^{-60} J^2}}{1.38 \times 10^{-29} J}} = \frac{0.618}{Z} = 0.618 = \frac{1}{\varphi} \quad (13)$$

where $\frac{1}{\varphi}$ is the inverse of the geometric constant gold-ratio φ and is given by

$$\frac{1}{\varphi} = \frac{-1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2} \quad (14)$$

which are the roots of the defining quadratic equation

$$\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = 1. \quad (15)$$

The positive root $\frac{1}{\varphi} = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} = 0.618 \dots$, which is a non-transcendental irrational number, is adopted here. Implicitly, all derived relations in this section and below, except for those on the Planck scale, are approximations reached on the basis of three significant digits.

According to Eqs. 10 and 13, the probability and energy level of state 2 are given by

$$p_2 = 1 - p_1 = 1 - \frac{1}{\varphi} = \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = \frac{\varphi - 1}{\varphi} \quad (16)$$

and

$$E_2 = 2E_1 = 2\sqrt{G \frac{kg^2}{km} h \frac{1}{s}}. \quad (17)$$

The summation of p_1 and p_2 fulfills the expectation that

$$p_1 + p_2 = e^{-\frac{\sqrt{G \frac{kg^2}{km} h \frac{1}{s}}}{kK}} + e^{-\frac{2\sqrt{G \frac{kg^2}{km} h \frac{1}{s}}}{kK}} = \frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = 1. \quad (18)$$

The energy levels of the two states may be expressed with φ as

$$E_1 = \sqrt{G \frac{kg^2}{km} h \frac{1}{s}} = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi} = -kK \ln \frac{1}{\varphi} \quad (19)$$

and

$$E_2 = 2 \sqrt{G \frac{kg^2}{km} h \frac{1}{s}} = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = -kK \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = -kK \ln \frac{\varphi^{-1}}{\varphi}. \quad (20)$$

Furthermore, the weighted amounts of energy of E_1 and E_2 are given by

$$p_1 E_1 = -\frac{1}{\beta} \times \frac{1}{\varphi} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi} = -kK \frac{1}{\varphi} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi} \quad (21)$$

and

$$p_2 E_2 = -\frac{1}{\beta} \times \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = -kK \frac{\varphi^{-1}}{\varphi} \ln \frac{\varphi^{-1}}{\varphi}. \quad (22)$$

Eq. 13 may be simplified to

$$\sqrt{Gh \frac{kg^2}{km \cdot s}} = kK \ln \varphi \quad (23)$$

compared with the form of Eq. 5. Eq. 23 may in turn be rearranged to

$$\frac{kg}{\sqrt{km \cdot sK}} = \frac{k \ln \varphi}{\sqrt{Gh}}. \quad (24)$$

When Eqs. 13 and 24 are expressed in the SI units kg , m , s and K , they are rewritten respectively as

$$p_1 = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-\frac{\sqrt{G \frac{kg^2}{m} h \frac{1}{s}}}{kK}} = \frac{1}{Z \varphi^{\sqrt{10^3}}} = \frac{1}{\varphi^{\sqrt{10^3}}} \quad (25)$$

and

$$\frac{kg}{\sqrt{m \cdot sK}} = \sqrt{\frac{10^3}{Gh}} k \ln \varphi \quad (26)$$

where

$$G = 6.67 \times 10^{-11} kg^{-1} m^3 s^{-2}; \quad (27)$$

$$h = 6.63 \times 10^{-34} kg m^2 s^{-1}; \quad (28)$$

$$k = 1.38 \times 10^{-23} kg m^2 s^{-2} K^{-1}. \quad (29)$$

Regarding the Planck units of length (l_p), mass (m_p), time (t_p) and temperature (T_p), they are defined using the physical constants h , G , k and c (the speed of light) as

$$l_p = \sqrt{\frac{hG}{c^3}}; \quad (30)$$

$$m_p = \sqrt{\frac{hc}{G}}; \quad (31)$$

$$t_p = \sqrt{\frac{hG}{c^5}}; \quad (32)$$

$$T_p = \sqrt{\frac{hc^5}{Gk^2}}; \quad (33)$$

The four physical quantities expressed in this natural unit system can be converted to the equivalent expressions in the SI units. On the Planck scale, the analogous expression of Eq. 24 is expected to be

$$\frac{m_p}{\sqrt{l_p t_p T_p}} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{hc}{G}}}{\frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{Gh}{c^3}} \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{\frac{Gh}{c^5}} \sqrt{\frac{hc^5}{Gk^2}}} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{hc}{G}}}{\sqrt{\frac{h^2 c}{k^2}}} = \frac{k}{\sqrt{Gh}} \quad (34)$$

whereas that of Eq. 13 is expected to be

$$p_1^P = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-\frac{\sqrt{\frac{Gm_p^2}{c^3}} h \frac{1}{t_p}}{kT_p}} = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-\frac{G \left(\sqrt{\frac{hc}{G}} \right)^2 h \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{Gh}{c^3}} \sqrt{\frac{Gh}{c^5}}}}{k \sqrt{\frac{hc^5}{Gk^2}}} = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-1} = \frac{1}{e} \quad (35)$$

which leaves the remaining portion of the probability space as

$$p_2^P = \frac{1}{Z} \left(1 - \frac{1}{e}\right) = 1 - \frac{1}{e} = \frac{e-1}{e} \quad (36)$$

again for $Z = 1$.

Thus, the geometric mean of gravitational energy and photon energy, which is calculated on the Planck scale and then normalized to kT_p , corresponds to a portion (p_1^P) of the probability space specified by $\frac{1}{e}$, and the remaining portion (p_2^P) is given by $\frac{e-1}{e}$ (Eqs. 35 and 36). In contrast, the mean energy, which is calculated in the units kg , km , s and K and then normalized to kK , corresponds to a portion (p_1) of the probability space specified by $\frac{1}{\varphi}$, and the remaining portion (p_2) is given by $\frac{\varphi-1}{\varphi}$ (Eqs. 13 and 16). In this context, the former is expressed with an e -based system and the latter appears to be expressible with an approximately φ -based system.

Furthermore, p_1^P or p_2^P is related to the energy level of E_1^P or E_2^P as

$$E_1^P = -\frac{1}{\beta_p} \ln p_1^P = -\frac{1}{\beta_p} \ln \frac{1}{e} = -kT_p \ln \frac{1}{e} = kT_p \quad (37)$$

or

$$E_2^P = -\frac{1}{\beta_p} \ln p_2^P = -\frac{1}{\beta_p} \ln \frac{e-1}{e} = -kT_p \ln \frac{e-1}{e} \quad (38)$$

and the weighted E_1^P or E_2^P is given by

$$p_1^P E_1^P = -\frac{1}{\beta_p} \times \frac{1}{e} \ln \frac{1}{e} = -kT_p \frac{1}{e} \ln \frac{1}{e} = kT_p \frac{1}{e} \quad (39)$$

or

$$p_2^P E_2^P = -\frac{1}{\beta_p} \times \frac{e-1}{e} \ln \frac{e-1}{e} = -kT_p \frac{e-1}{e} \ln \frac{e-1}{e}. \quad (40)$$

Discussion

Eqs 13 and 16 are expressed on a very different set of physical scale than Eqs. 35 and 36 are. The state probabilities in the former pair are expressed with an approximately φ -based system whereas those in the latter pair are expressed in an e -based system. Despite this difference, Eq. 13 shares the same mathematical form with Eq. 35, so does Eq. 16 with Eq. 36. This comparison highlights the mathematical elegance of these probability expressions.

Eq. 21, 22, 39 or 40, each of which expresses the weighted energy of a state, is in the form of the natural logarithmic function

$$g(x) = \frac{1}{x} \ln x = -\frac{1}{x} \ln \frac{1}{x}. \quad (41)$$

The derivative of Eq. 41 was used to solve Steiner's calculus problem, i.e., to identify the maximum of the function

$$f(x) = x^{\frac{1}{x}} \quad (42)$$

which occurs at $x = e$. In Eq. 39, the value of $-\frac{1}{e} \ln \frac{1}{e} = \frac{1}{e}$, which is calculated to be 0.368 ..., corresponds to the maximum of the function defined by Eq. 41. Interestingly, the value of $-\frac{1}{\varphi^2} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = -\frac{\varphi-1}{\varphi} \ln \frac{\varphi-1}{\varphi}$ in Eq. 22, which is also calculated to be 0.368 ..., is very close but is not exactly equal to the maximal value though. It is noteworthy that each term in Gibbs' expression of entropy, i.e., $-p_i \ln p_i$, also has the same form of Eq. 41.

The counterpart of Eq. 18 in terms of the arithmetic average of gravitational energy and photon energy would be

$$e^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2}(G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1})}{kK \times 10^{23}}} + e^{-\frac{G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1}}{kK \times 10^{23}}} = \frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = 1. \quad (43)$$

It is noteworthy that here, the φ -based partition of a probability space more closely approximates the distribution of energy that is expressed in terms of the arithmetic average of specified amounts of gravitational energy and photon energy than that in terms of the geometric average of specified amounts of energy (see [7] for other relevant expressions in the form of the arithmetic average). This difference stems from the slight difference between the significant digits of G and h and, consequently, their arithmetic average is, by definition, slightly larger than their geometric average.

On the basis of Eqs. 24, 26 and 34, the apparent relations among the physical constants and three unit systems may be summarized as

$$\frac{k}{\sqrt{Gh}} = \frac{m_p}{\sqrt{l_p t_p T_p}} = \frac{1.00}{\ln \varphi} \times \frac{kg}{\sqrt{km \cdot sK}} = \frac{1.00}{\sqrt{10^3} \ln \varphi} \times \frac{kg}{\sqrt{m \cdot sK}}. \quad (44)$$

The number 1.00 explicitly indicates Eq. 44 is expressed under the condition of three significant digits. Arguably, it is intuitive that a ratio of physical units (e.g., $\frac{kg}{\sqrt{km \cdot sK}}$) approximately equals a compound constant ($\frac{k \ln \varphi}{\sqrt{Gh}}$) in the context that mass (in kg) is taken as not only itself but also the source of energy, whereas the length dimension (in km) and the time dimension (in s) together are viewed as the combined residence of energy (or mass) and the temperature (in K) as the manifestation of energy.

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